

Paper 24

**OUTSOURCING: RECENT TRENDS IN
MANAGEMENT FOR DEVELOPING INDIA**

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Abstract:-

Entire world is a jointed with each other due to globalization. IT plays a vital role in it. By using IT techniques and new trends in Management, India can be take opportunity to be a developed country. This new trends of management is Outsourcing. Now a day developed countries outsource too many jobs to India. Such benefit should also to be taken by Indian. Indians Entrepreneurs are sharp minded, hard worker, creative, etc., just need to do some financial management, time management and stress management. To manage all these things need to accept foreign strategy i.e. Outsourcing. Outsourcing is strategic management model transferring business process to other country.

As per a rapid growth of Indian Economy, very soon India will become a Developed Country. As compare to other developing country, India moves upward in rank. Thus it beneficial as India can outsource their work to other country. And concentrate on main or core functions of the business. It helps to increase productivity, quality of product, reduction in cost, expansion of business, profit making and etc.

This research paper discusses and focuses on various criteria of outsourcing which is useful for Entrepreneurs. Paper also evaluates the benefits and the challenges in outsourcing and offshoring. To take the reap of outsourcing, Indian Entrepreneurs must be accepted the outsourcing opportunity. This paper discusses that how Indians Entrepreneurs use this new trends in Management i.e. outsourcing and become developed country very soon.

Key Words:- Outsourcing, Entrepreneurs, Management.

Introduction:

India is developing country. The dream of Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam was to make India as a developed nation in the world. Dr. Kalam said India will become developed nation because by the year 2020. To achieve such biggest dream of big person is really attribute him. Outsourcing is the right path for transfer this dream into reality. Today in global world, too many developed country outsource their work to India. But it is not sufficient to achieve our

target, thus it is necessary that India also use offshore outsourcing. This paper discussed how Indian do offshore, benefit of offshore outsourcing, where India can be outsource, etc.

Outsourcing-

Outsourcing means when a company contracts with an outside company for services or other business processes, rather than employing in the own company. These services may be provided on-site or off-site.

Outsourcing is one of the fastest growing segments of BPO and ITES industry. BPO is a strategy which promotes in a unique way either by putting in new technology or applying existing technology to improve a process. IT-enabled outsourcing services use information technology in the processing and delivery of the services. These services are typically delivered through a telecommunications or data network, or other electronic media.

India in the recent years has as shown huge developments in the areas of communication, power and software developments. It has already established itself as a global BPO hub and is fast becoming a popular outsourcing destination for major manufactures across the globe.

Types of Outsourcing

There are two kinds of outsourcing, namely near-shore outsourcing, onshore outsourcing and off-shore outsourcing.

1) Off-shore outsourcing

Off-shore outsourcing means that some of the company's work is done by people with other countries.

2) On-shore outsourcing

On-shore outsourcing is also called domestic outsourcing. It means that work or service of the company is done by another company in the same country.

There are too many countries which currency value is less than India. T take the benefit of such currency value India can use offshore outsourcing. It means Indian can be outsourcing their work to other country.

Research Methodology:

Objectives:

Main objective of the research articles find out the various countries to whom India can be outsource. To discuss various point which motivate to India for offshore outsourcing. To study of benefits of offshore outsourcing to India.

Data Collection:

This article is based on Primary and Secondary data. Secondary data are collected though the web survey of Entrepreneurs, books, articles, newspapers, reports etc. On the basis of secondary data the primary data is collected through the observation method.

Data Analysis and Interpretations:-

Outsourcing Partner:-

Outsourcing Partner means organizations to whom outsourcing work is given. The partner may be within country or outside of the country. Entrepreneurs select their outsourcing partner as per the requirements and convenience.

➤ Off-shore Outsourcing:-

Off-shore outsourcing means outsource the work to other country. There are too many countries which are under develop than India. As well as their currency rate is also less than India. So Indian can outsource to that country can take benefits of cost reduction. The following table show the list of countries whose currency is less than India.

Name of Country	Rate of Exchange with India
Vietnam	1 Rupee = 333.98 Vietnamese Dong
Indonesia	1 Rupee = 197.02 Indonesian Rupaiah
Laos	124.89 LAK
Paraguay	1 Rupee = 83.31 Paraguayan Guarani
Cambodia	1 Rupee = 61.29 Cambodian Riel
Uzbekistan	1 Rupee = 44.76 Uzbekistani Som
Mongolia	1 Rupee = 33.31 Mongolian Tugrik

If Indian Entrepreneurs outsource their work to these countries it is benefited as cost reduction. The following table show the cost difference of India and other countries due to exchange rate. In other words to take the benefit of high exchange value of Indian Rupee, Indian Entrepreneurs should control cost.

Cost Saving Comparison:-

Bookkeeper/Jr. Accountant	Indian Employee	Offshore Cost			
		Vietnam	Indonesia	Laos	Paraguay

Monthly Salary	35000	104.80	177.65	280.25	420.12
Other Charges (10%)	3500	--	--	--	--
Total Cost	38500	104.80	177.65	280.25	420.12

(Source: Primary Data)

This table shows cost saving comparison when Indian outsource to other country. All these countries are capable to do every types of outsourcing work. It means India can outsource any type of work. The processes or activities that are being outsourced could range from customer service and telemarketing to IT management software development, market research and even financial portfolio management. The services that can be outsourced to other countries. The following table shows the literacy rate of country.

Name of Country	Literacy Rate
Vietnam	93.7%
Indonesia	95.38%
Laos	84.66%
Paraguay	94.66%
Cambodia	78.3%
Uzbekistan	83.8%

Benefits of Outsourcing:

Outsource the work to other countries is benefited as:

- Cost Saving.
- Concentrate on Core functions of business.
- Saving on infrastructure and technology.
- Saving the resources.
- Faster and Better Services.

1. Cost Saving-

The most observable and evident benefit relates to the cost savings that outsourcing brings about. Work can be done at a lower cost and with better quality. Due to the difference in wages between India and other countries, the same kind of work that is done over there can be done in India at a higher of the cost. There is a cost savings of around 70% to 80% by outsourcing your work to other countries.

2. Focus on core areas-

Businessman can be free due to Outsourcing. Businessman can be free from unnecessary process of business and enable to focus on building brand, invest in research and development and move on to providing higher value added services.

3. Save on infrastructure and technology-

Due to outsourcing reduce the investment in infrastructure as the outsourcing partner takes the responsibility of the business processes and hence develops infrastructure for the same.

4. Saving the Resources-

Outsource to other countries is benefited as saving of other resources of production. For production purpose need various factors or resources such as machinery, manpower, factory, etc., such types or resources can be save with the help of outsourcing.

5. Faster and better services-

Make service offerings better with high quality deliverables and decrease the lead time it takes for product to reach the marketplace. Thus you would be faster in getting ideas converted into products and better at delivering the value-added proposition.

Conclusion:

Outsourcing is new management trend for developing Entrepreneurial skills with help of ICT. It benefited to entrepreneurs as cost saving, concentrate on core functions, concentration on market etc. It not only benefited to entrepreneurs but Indian economy also such as increase source of national income, increase source of employment opportunities, development of all states and cities, reduce heavy burden of particular cities. At glance outsourcing increase the growth rate of Indian economy and push it towards developed country and make sure India will become developed country very soon.

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